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CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND STORE ATTRIBUTES: A STUDY OF DELHI & NCR

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ABSTRACT

This paper is intended to investigate the extent of relationship between consumer purchase intention and attribute of retail outlet like ambience, product assortment, and store atmosphere.

This study has been conducted in Delhi and its nearby region between December and March 2015. Convenience sampling is used to collect data at various mall intercepts. A total of 250 structured questionnaires were used, out of which 25 questionnaire were not completely filled and hence not included in study. The study reveals a very strong association between different stores attributes and purchase intentions. The study would definitely help the practitioners to adopt the strategies that would retain existing customers and attract new customers.

Key words: Purchase Intention, Store Attributes, Product Assortment, Store Atmosphere

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian retail landscape is changing day by day, the small formats are either dying or they have been forced to adopt the way the global players are following. As a market India always been a center stage for Global retailers, because of its demography, demand and changing culture. Information technology has also played a pivotal role in today's retail business and dramatically changed the rule of game. The global players are using all the tactical means to attract enormous footfall and converting them profitably. The corporate culture and excellent operational efficiency that they bring has completely changed the way of shopping of Indian consumer.

Efforts have been inclined to understand the extent to which consumers purchase intention is getting affected by store attributes like location, product assortments and store ambience.

Product assortment means the product mix i.e. product line, product width, product depth, the retailers are offering to consumer within their store. A good product assortment in a retail store may become a one point shopping experience for consumer. Store ambience and Store atmospherics includes; store layout, furniture and fixtures, lighting schemes, color selection, user friendly shelves with enough depth, pleasing music, and positively stimulating smell. All these Characteristics will generate a positive assessment of the store.

Location is the factor which is of utmost importance in retailing and plays a very crucial role for consumer store choice. A favorable location shall be a place that consumer perceives is quite good and reasonable for shopping with ample availability of public transports, well wide parking area and consumer friendly environment. A location that suits to consumer is instrumental in retail success.

Intention of purchase is customer willingness to purchase a specific product or service from a retailer, and decision may be the result of impact of attributes of the store like product assortment, Store atmosphere and location.

The purpose of this study is to investigate and understand the extent, to which these characteristics would influence the Indian consumer's store selection.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Reilly 1931; Huff 1964; see Hubbard 1978 and Brown 1989 for reviews of this work; Baumol and Idle 1956 makes a similar argument said in the foundational theory of choice that Now a day it is commonly said theory that most of the customers like and have a preference to large assortments and a large range of products. The likelihood of the selection of a store typically and largely depends on store size, and its assortment size and is inversely dependent on distance from home
2. Finn and Louviere (1996) found that among all the store image attributes, only product assortment and price place great variances in choices. Availability of great breadth of different products offered by a store has a great amount of impact on consumer's perception about store and retail image. Hoch, Bradlow and Wansink (1999) determined that product attributes affect consumers' perceptions of an assortment. Also in another study it is examined that product attributes, style, colors, and SKU's is counted in product assortment (Terry.J). However, the number of brands and sizes are attributes that can be applied sparingly across categories (Boatwright and Nunes 2001). Here in this research we have chosen following measures of category 1. Number of brands offered, 2. Number of sizes per brand, 3. Style and colors, 4. Availability of a household's favorite brands, 5. Private brand 6. Number of stock-keeping units projected.
3. Keller (2003) investigated that because availability under one roof enables customer to avail many advantages. First the great the width of the range, the greater the number of different situations under which a retailer is recalled, and is considered by the consumer as noted by the . Secondly, the one stop shopping convenience that a broad product range enables more important than ever for consumers with limited time today.
4. Messinger and Narasimhan 1997 said that increasing pressures on retailers to broaden their range. Also the depth of the retail assortment affects so much on consumer store choice. Variety seeking consumers will perceive greater convenience as the perceived assortment of brands, flavors and sizes increases (McAlister and Pessemier 1982; Kahn and Wansink 2004), consumers will believe they have more elasticity in their choices who have vague future preferences (Kahn and Lehmann 1991), and there are more chances that those consumers locate the item they desire. Private brand assortment is very much popular in many stores also with manufactures' brand.
5. Steenkamp and Dekimpe (1997) investigated that a motivation for offering private labels is the highest percent margins (Hoch and Banerji 1993), and second, the implicit assumption that providing a private label brand generates loyalty to the store. Baumol and Ide (1956) and Brown (1978) observed that stores which offer more product assortment, for those consumers are willing to travel farther to those stores than those which offer low assortment. Assortment is multidimensional – Broniarczyk, Hoyer and McAlister (1998) determined that three factors

affect consumers' perceptions of assortment in a category—the amount of shelf space devoted to the category and the number of SKUs, and the availability of the consumer's favorite item (note that the terms "item," "product" and "SKUs" will be used interchangeably).

6. Greenleaf and Lehmann (1995); Karni and Schwartz (1977) found that large assortment also help shopper and to increase sale and give surety of sale that by seeing large assortment and a big range of products shopper might prefer to purchase from that store by minimizing the ambiguity of that available assortment is not good enough for selection, and large assortment also eliminate the thinking of shopper that available assortment is not envoy of all good brands or products and might be another store have more good variety of products available and shopper think that he/she should go to other stores.
7. Cadenat (2003) found thatthere are some factors which favor in reduced or decreased assortment. It is the limited space in the store. As if we are saying that increased assortment increase our sale but it is constrained here that every retailer is unable to increase store space and shelf space.
8. Liao, Liaw, & Jen argued that the store staff and store design can influence the shopping mood, not music. It is also possible, satisfaction affected by emotions of shopping through mediating role of consumption behavior. Consumer experience of positive emotions in the shop will generate a positive assessment of the stock.
9. Jain & Bagdare (2011) reveal that retail store music experience stimulates the consumption level in terms of behavioral, cognitive and emotional reactions, visibility and attitude, the money and spending time in the shop as well. The consumer profile, the profile store, market timing and environmental cues moderate the impact of music on purchasing behavior. Slow-tempo music perceive positive service quality and low arousing cues have mediating effects on consumer's perception but fast tempo music and high arousing cues have indirect effect on consumer perception (Michon & Chebat, 2006).
10. Oh, Fiorito, Cho, & Hofacker, (2007) found that the effect of store atmosphere on consumer expectations about the quality of products and store image as a mediator, either web-based shop, or a brick and mortar store. Findings support previous studies which have shown that consumer purchase intentions can be affected by store image and consumer expectations. Retail stores must utilize unproductive area by providing wide aisle, which facilitate the movement of customers throughout the store. Aisle deign would influence the pattern of traffic flow towards the merchandising .Lighting consider as a mood setter tool. It can be bright, and soft lights, which flow throughout the display area. Retailers use these sophisticated lights at regular interval for the sake of customer attention. For various behaviour and situations, lighting preferences varies individual to individual (Butler & Biner 1987).
11. Sadalla, Veshure, & Burroughs, (1987) investigated that as compare to bright lighting, soft light create more pleasant and soothing mood (Meer 1985). Research suggests that home Interior décor express the self concept and social status (Lauman & House, 1973), (Jin, 1990; Joy & Dholakia, 1991; Lauman & House, 1973) Likewise stores have self image and personality (Martineau, 1958) and it can be communicated to the customers through store interior designing Greenberg, Sherman, &Shiffman, 1983 ; Rich & Portis, 1964)(Greenberg et al., 1983; Kotler, 1973). Pleasant environmental odor had positive effect on evaluations of in store atmosphere, available merchandising and intend the customers to visit the store again and again (Sprangenberg et al., 1996). Results indicate that fragranced store display generates the most positive responses and pleasurable experiences (Fiore, Yah, & Yoh, 2000).

12. (Zentes, morschett, & schramm) said that Selection of store location is a long-term decision which requires a long-term capital dedication in this context store location is considered one of the most important element in retail marketing strategy. The choice of a store location has a deep effect on the entire business of a retail operation. For selecting a most favorable store-site, it is important to consider the demographic factors of that area including age, income, traffic patterns, family size, competition and related kind of retail outlets.
13. Byrom, Retail Location Analysis: A Case Study of Burger King & McDonald's in Portage & Summit Counties, Ohio, (2005) has discussed Geographic information system which is being utilized now a day for analyzing the structure of retail activities with location data. Geographic information system collect and transform the several databases into a common set of database (Pettit, 1999) Three key factors such as distance traveled to get to the store, size of the store, and the retail image of the store based on its products, easy accessibility, visibility, parking are used in Gravity Model (Mercurio, 1984). For getting the competitive advantage for retailers Decision support systems is also becoming a significant source. While selecting a location an important factor which must be considered is examining the distance that a customer has to travel. The distances which customers want to travel are depending upon the type of product to be purchased. On the base of specialty or commodity product number of the trips made by consumers and the travel time will be different (Salvaneschi, 1996).
14. Engel et. al (1995) said that First step is Problem identification, than search out the information about the problem, evaluating the alternatives, finally customer make a purchase on these basis. Post-purchase behavior develops through these steps. Sometimes consumers buy the product in store that is more attractive and make a decision on the spot. The intention of purchasing the consumer may be impulse buying or partially pre-programmed and can be fully pre-planned. In impulse buying behavior of consumers to make the decision and make an instant purchase of the product that is more attractive to him, partly in pre-planned the consumer to choose the product type and model, but choose the brand in the store and completely preplanned for an existing customer to choose the product and the brand he will buy (Engel JF Blackwell, 1995).
15. Shwu-Ing Wu and Chen- Lien Lo, (2009) investigated that Brand awareness, consumer perception and brand association has a significant impact on purchase intent Consumer sentiment and the situation may affect their impulsive purchase intent. Consumer sentiment include the personal taste of the situation and express that impulse purchase intent of consumers differ due to variation in a situation such as prices increase more than customer expectations (Kotler, 2003). Brand awareness increase brand loyalty, consumer confidence and purchases intent for the consumer (Aaker, . D., 1990).

3. Design of Hypothesis

H1: purchase intention is strongly influenced by Product assortment

H2: There is a significant impact of location on purchase intention

H3: store atmospherics plays an instrumental role in purchase intention

4. Working Methodology

The objective of the study is to analyze the degree of association between retail store attributes and Purchase intentions of consumer in Delhi and NCR. The convenience cum random sampling (Two stages

Sampling) was adapted in the study and the primary data from 250 customers was collected with the help of structured questionnaire consisting of various closed ended questions directly from the consumers in retail stores. 225 questionnaires found appropriate in all respect to analyze the data. Percentage analysis, inter variable correlation and regression analysis are used to interpret the findings.

5. Research Results and Discussions

5.1 Demographic Profile

Table 1 shows that 41.8% of male and 58.2% female respondents, it shows that more females are making purchasing as compared to men.

Table 2 shows that majority of respondents (38.2%) are graduates.

Table 3 shows that majority of respondents are in age group of 26-33 (33.3%) years and 34-41 years (29.3%) both of this age group alone contains around 62.6 % of total respondents. Therefore, it may be concluded that most of the shoppers are in 26-41 years of age.

Table 4 shows that most of the respondents are having disposable income between 21000-30000 (36.4%).

Table 5 shows that majority of respondents are visiting once in a month (50.7%) and once in a fortnight (40.9%) to the stores.

Table 1: Gender of respondent

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	94	41.8	41.8	41.8
Female	131	58.2	58.2	100.0
Total	225	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Educational Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Upto 10th Class	38	16.9	16.9	16.9
Intermediate	39	17.3	17.3	34.2
Graduation	86	38.2	38.2	72.4
Post Graduation	45	20.0	20.0	92.4
P.hD and Above	17	7.6	7.6	100.0
Total	225	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 : Age in year

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-25 years	23	10.2	10.2	10.2
26-33 years	75	33.3	33.3	43.6
34-41 years	66	29.3	29.3	72.9
42-49 years	54	24.0	24.0	96.9
50 and above	7	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total	225	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Disposable Income

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid below 10000	15	6.7	6.7	6.7
11000-20000	38	16.9	16.9	23.6
21000-30000	82	36.4	36.4	60.0
31000-40000	79	35.1	35.1	95.1
41000 and above	11	4.9	4.9	100.0
Total	225	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 : Frequency of Store Visit

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid once in a week	19	8.4	8.4	8.4
Once in a fortnight	92	40.9	40.9	49.3
Once in a month	114	50.7	50.7	100.0
Total	225	100.0	100.0	

5.2 Pearson’s Moment Correlation

Table 6 : Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Product Assortment	2.3111	0.43268	225
Store Atmosphere	4.1667	0.36992	225
Location	3.7167	0.68554	225
Purchase Intention	4.1278	0.48172	225

Table 7: Correlations

		Product Assortment	Store Atmosphere	Location	Purchase Intention
Product Assortment	Pearson Correlation	1	.637**	.544**	.297**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	225	225	225	225
Store Atmosphere	Pearson Correlation	.637**	1	.565**	.565**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	225	225	225	225
Location	Pearson Correlation	.544**	.565**	1	.563**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	225	225	225	225
Purchase Intention	Pearson Correlation	.297**	.132**	.563**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	225	225	225	225

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

For investigation of the influence of Product assortment, Store atmosphere and location on Purchase intention, moment correlation of Pearson has been determined. It is very much obvious from Table 7 Mean value of Product assortment is 2.3111 that simply depicts that consumers is not giving enormous importance while making purchasing intentions from a particular store. As we can see that 2.3111, is very less far from 5 that also strengthening our conclusion. While, standard Deviation is 0.43268, which indicates a fair variation among the responses of the consumers.

In Table 7 it is also being well depicted that Product assortment and store atmosphere (4.1667) is very strongly correlated, while there is a moderate association between location and purchase intention (3.7167), conclusion may be drawn on these findings that if the product assortments are great then location may be compromised by the consumers. The Store atmosphere is playing an instrumental role in the purchase intention of consumer (4.1667) which is also very much close to 5, the standard deviation in this case is 0.68 which shows almost 70% variation in the responses of the consumers.

From Table 8 we can see that store atmosphere, product assortments and the location are has to be in tandem in order to attract, transact and retain consumers with business. While all of these three

attributes do have their own importance and influence in shaping the intention of the consumers toward purchasing from a particular retail store.

5.3 Regression Analysis

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.647 ^a	.396	.384	.44692

a. Predictors: (Constant), Location, Product Assortment, Store Atmosphere

Table 9: ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.469	3	6.823	35.389	.000 ^a
	Residual	33.592	186	.187		
	Total	54.061	189			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Location, Product Assortment, Store Atmosphere

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

Table 10: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.962	.254		7.702	.000
	Product Assortment	.168	.109	.139	1.611	.112
	Store Atmosphere	-.162	.060	-.231	-3.013	.002
	Location	.580	.072	.632	9.106	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

For establishing relationship between Product assortment, Store atmosphere, location and Purchase intention linear regression has been applied

It is very much clear from Table 8 that there is 64% variation(R = .647) in product assortment, store atmosphere, and location on purchase intention. The coefficient of determination shows that there is 39 % (0.396) total variation with its linear relationship. In Table 9 the analysis of variance (ANOVA) depicts the level of significance, it is very much less than 0.05, hence we can establish a relationship that purchase intention is very much influenced by store location, product assortment and store atmospherics.

The value of the constant for regression equation can be found from table 10, which is 1.962 and clearly employing that if the product assortment would be zero then the average of purchase intention

will be the constant. While beta value of .168 shows that there will be 0.168 unit increases in purchase intention if there would be one unit increase in product assortment.

The linear regression equation will be of the following form as from table 10.

Purchase intention = 1.962 + .168(product assortment) + -.162 (store atmosphere) + .580 (location)

The above linear regression model clearly depicts that one percent product assortment will bring 17% change in purchase intention of the consumer, when the other two factors in the consideration would be kept constant i.e. zero. While keeping product assortment and location constant, one unit decrease in store atmosphere will decrease around 16% of the purchase intentions of the consumers. When product assortment and store atmosphere be kept constant, the beta value of 0.580 will contribute 58%. It can also be noticed from table 10 that there is no co linearity among responses exists.

6. Scope and limitations

Since the scope of present study is limited to Delhi and NCR, one of the states of India, it can be carried out at national and international level. The research was not inclined to either one store or one format so the results can't be generalized. The scope of present study can further be expanded in the context of different geographic, demographic and socio-cultural variables which could not be included in the present study. By considering the present research as a base further research on purchase intention as a result of store attribute can be carried out for in depth analysis of the subject. Retailers marketing activities are increasing with the growth of more informed and demanding consumers. Due to this research can be extended to find out the best practices for stimulating consumer purchase intention for a particular store.

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